

ISic0666

I.Sicily inscription 0666

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object

statue base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Segesta

Place of origin (modern)

Segesta

Provenance

SAS 4

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Segesta, excavation stores, inventory SG1181

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Municipium

Apparatus

Text of Ampolo and Erdas 2019

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491375

EDCS 5000363

Bibliography

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Michelini, C. 1997. Le agorai di ambiente coloniale e il caso di Segesta.
Seconde giornate internazionali di studi sull'area elima (Gibellina 22-26 ottobre 1994). Pisa, Gibellina. pp. 1139-1158. At 1142 n.10

Ampolo, Carmine, Erdas, Donatella 2019. *Inscriptiones Segestanae. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Segesta*. Pisa. At L4

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0666. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4338165>